

More on the red spider *Theridion delicatum* O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1904 (Araneae: Theridiidae) from South Africa

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ABSTRACT: *Theridion delicatum* O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1904 a species that was described from the Cape Flat, Cape Peninsula, South Africa some 121 years ago. The species has now a wider distribution and has been recorded from seven provinces. The general morphology of the species is discussed based on photographs of live specimens, with notes on their behaviour, distribution in South Africa, and conservation status.

INTRODUCTION

A female of *Theridion delicatum* O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1904 was first recorded and described from the Cape Flat, Cape Peninsula, South Africa, some 121 years ago. Since then, nothing has been reported on the species. During surveys of the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA), large numbers of theridiids were sampled, but unfortunately, due to a lack of taxonomic revision, numerous species could not be identified (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2025).

Between the SANSA samples, there were numerous theridiid specimens recognized by their bright red colour. In search of a species name, the only red theridiid found in the literature belongs to the genus *Rubrorridion* Wunderlich, 2011, with the type species *Theridion musivum* Simon, 1898 (Vanuytven, 2021). However, the somatic features of *R. musivum* differ from the specimens sampled in South Africa in several characters. Unfortunately, this striking red colour fades in specimens preserved in alcohol. This warrants a reexamination of the *Theridion* species described from South Africa, not only focusing on the red body colour.

The somatic characters and drawings of a South African endemic species described by O.P.-Cambridge (1904) from Constantia Flats in the Western Cape correspond with this spider. Outstanding characters are the large, almost globular, orange-yellow abdomen (in alcohol) that partly covers the carapace. The abdomen is marked faintly with a white longitudinal central line with 2-3 slightly oblique lines on each side. The lines on the abdomen are formed by minute white spots (O.P.-Cambridge, 1904). He also stated that it is possible that other specimens, when found, will exhibit some modification in colour and markings. The general morphology of the species is discussed based on photographs of live specimens, with notes on their behaviour, distribution in South Africa, and conservation status.

TAXONOMY

Theridion delicatum O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1904

Theridion delicatum O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1904: 157;
Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2021: 29.

Description: Female as described by Pickard-Cambridge (1904) from alcohol material. Cephalothorax pale yellowish white. Eyes in two rows, nearly equal in size (Fig. 5); eyes on black spots; eyes in two rows of equal length; anterior row slightly recurved and posterior row slightly procurved; median ocular quadrangle form a square (Figs 3 & 5); clypeus wide; chelicerae moderate long; sternum round broadly truncated posteriorly; few longish bristles on the caput directed forwards; the longest setae in a transverse line at the middle of the central quadrangle.

Figure 1–3. *Theridion delicatum*. 1. Female from Ferncliff near Boulder Dam (Alan Manson). 2. Female from Paarl (Cecile Roux) 3. Female from Rayton (Peter Webb).

Figures 4–11. *Theridion delicatum*. 4–7. Line drawings. 4. Body lateral view. 5. Eye pattern. 6. Epigyne. 7. Female habitus clearly showing the setae on the abdomen. 8. Showing the colour in a live specimen. 9. Compared to specimen from alcohol. 10. Eye pattern. 11. Female epigyne. Credits: 4–7. After Pickard-Cambridge (1904). 8. Linda Wiese. 9. Ansie Dippenaar-Schoeman. 10–11. Peter Webb.

Abdomen large, almost globular; projecting largely over the carapace (Fig. 4); in alcohol a dull orange-yellow marked faintly with a white longitudinal central line (Fig. 9); two or three horizontal short lines on each side of central line and forming a band around the anterior edge; lines on abdomen formed by minute white spots; dorsum with numerous long backwards directed setae (Fig. 1). Legs moderately long; 1423 slender; furnished with fine setae and slender bristles; same colour as cephalothorax; femora and tibiae of leg IV dark and as also less strongly those of the other legs (Figs 7 & 8). Male undescribed.

VARIATION: In live specimens the body and legs are usually red (Figs 1–3). The carapace is red with only the eyes on black spots (Fig. 10). The abdomen colour varies from a uniform red in some specimens (Fig. 12), while in others the abdomen is decorated with white lines (Figs 8, 13, 21). In some, there are dark bands present on both sides of the median white band (Figs 14 & 15). The colour of the legs varies from red with no dark bands to red with only leg IV banded (Fig. 3) or red with all the femora dark (Fig. 12) to almost completely black legs (Figs 16 & 17).

LIFESTYLE

They do not make a web and run around on the plants and ground. With their small size and red colour they resemble some of the Erythraeidae mites (Figs 18–19). The egg sac is covered by an uneven layer of silk and seems to be carried around by the female (Fig. 16). Fig. 16 show a male and female busy to mate.

Figures 12–21 *Theridion delicatum*. 13. Female from Wynford (Peter Webb). 13. Female from Riebeeck West (Cecile Rouw). 14. Female from Loskopdam (Peter Webb). 15. Female from East Londen (Simon and Eunete Van Wyk-Schumacher). 16. Mating (Simon and Eunete Van Wyk-Schumacher). 17. Female with egg sac (Linda Wiese). 18–21. Mites species resembling *T. delicatum* (Peter Webb).

DISTRIBUTION

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa, Zimbabwe (iNat).

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA (Fig. 22)

Figure 22. Distribution records of *Theridion delicatum* in South Africa. Showing the SANSA distribution records of material housed in the National Collection of Arachnida and the locations of iNaturalist “Research Grade” observations of *Theridion delicatum* from <https://www.inaturalist.org> exported on 24 September 2025.

DISCUSSION

When the African *Theridion* species are eventually revised this species may be placed in a new genus or it might be a new species in *Rubroridion*.

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Figures 20–21. *Theridion delicatum*. 22. Immature male (Peter Webb). 23. Female on plant (Simon and Eunete Van Wyk-Schumacher).

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